

**Does Zambia Conform to the Economic Theory of Conflict and Other Theories
Explaining the Causes of Civil Wars?**

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ABSTRACT

Africa has experienced many civil wars. According to Obwona and Guloba (2009) Africa during the period 1990-2000 saw 19 armed conflicts in different parts of the continent. The continent is therefore prone to civil wars. This paper focuses on Zambia whether the country conforms to the ingredients proposed in Economic Theory of Conflict and other theories as the major causes of civil wars and whether Zambia can provide insight in the prevention of conflicts so African countries and others can concentrate on providing sustainable development.

Keywords: Civil conflicts, civil war economic theory of conflict, theories of causes of wars, Zambia no conflict

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